

TEACHING IELTS READING TO YOUNG LEARNERS: SOME TEACHING IDEAS

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ABSTRACT

The recent IELTS statistics show that more than three million International English Language Testing System (IELTS) tests were taken in 2017 – a dramatic increase from the 43,000 IELTS tests taken in 1995. In Vietnam for the past decades, IELTS has gained increasing popularity and it is widely accepted as a reliable evaluation of English language proficiency in the Vietnamese Education sector. Another trend in Vietnam is a growing number of young learners have prepared for IELTS and taken the tests. Teaching IELTS reading to young learners can be challenging because guiding the learners toward achieving a high IELTS band score can be a long process involving the introduction, development and mastery of various techniques including skimming and scanning, recognizing paraphrases, text analysis, techniques for dealing with the various question types and time management. Teaching IELTS reading lessons to young learners can be communicative and rewarding with some suggested teaching ideas and practical activities, currently applied in a center for foreign languages.

Key words: communicative, IELTS reading, young learners

1 INTRODUCTION

The communicative approach in language teaching starts from a theory of language as communication (Maryslessor, Barasa & Omulando, 2014). This approach aims to put into practice procedures for the four language skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing) that recognize the interrelation of language and communication. Of different principles of this approach, diversifying skills and activities in the classrooms is very fundamental and practical (Desai, 2015). It means language should be taught by integrating all language skills and not by only one skill. With communicative approach, teaching is not limited to only speaking skill, but such receptive skills as reading should be developed. Teachers should design and carry out communicative activities, or engaging activities to encourage teacher-learner and learner-learner interaction in the target language (Albate, 2014).

2 CHALLENGES OF APPLYING COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING (CLT) FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

For teaching young learners, there have been debates about whether approaches to CLT originally used for adult English education in Western countries where groups are small and classrooms well-equipped are still suitable (Copland, Garton & Burns, 2014). In many Vietnamese EFL

classes, it is challenging to effectively apply learner-centered teaching (Li, 1998), or carry out class activities in pairs and in groups (Hoque, 2009). Another challenge for teaching young learners is the problem of control and discipline because young learners generally have short attention span (Musthafa, 2010). Unlike adult learners who can concentrate hours and hours on the topic they are working on, many children can hold their attention for about 15 to 20 minutes on one activity. It can also be difficult to motivate young learners. Young learners' motivation to learn English may vary due to the heterogeneity in the classroom in terms of students' readiness level to learn English (Asmali, 2017). In addition, in many EFL contexts, children may struggle to understand the relevance of learning English (Ho, 2003, Li, 1998).

For an effective environment to promote young learners' English language development, teachers should provide plenty of comprehensible input, that is, children should clearly understand what is being communicated; teachers should organize more interactive tasks, focusing on pairwork and groupwork; teachers should choose teaching materials or subject matters which are appropriate for age and grade levels; teachers should ensure low anxiety for the young learners and importantly, teachers should maximize the use of English (Kersten & Rohde, 2013).

3 IELTS READING

The IELTS Reading test lasts for 60 minutes, including the time to read, comprehend the passages and answer the questions. Candidates take either the Academic or General Training Reading module. Both modules consist of three sections, with different question types, which are used to assess comprehension. In both tests the sections or passages are in order of increasing difficulty. Each reading passage has several questions of different types, which may appear before or after a passage. A variety of questions are chosen from the following typical question types: multiple choice, short answer questions, sentence completion, notes/summary/diagram/flow chart/table completion, choosing from a 'heading bank' for identified paragraphs, identification of the writer's views (yes/no/not given) or identification of information in the text (true/false/not given), classification, matching lists/phrases. With these kinds of questions, different reading skills are tested including identifying the gist of a passage; finding detailed factual information in a passage; identifying relationship between ideas or information items, such as cause and effect order of events, comparison; making inferences; distinguishing between facts, assumption or opinion; understanding text organization; and summarizing information (British Council, 2017).

4 SOME IDEAS OF APPLYING CLT TO TEACH IELTS READING

Teaching IELTS reading can be an arduous task as it is often difficult to know how to improve students' skills. The main aim of reading is comprehension. Chowdhury (2009) used the definition of reading by The Oxford Companion to the English Language as "the process of extracting meaning from written or printed language...". According to the author, for an effective comprehension, the reader's background knowledge should integrate with the text to create the meaning. Communication, as commonly perceived, suggests interaction of some sort, generally between speaker and listener; and reading, therefore, often seems a solitary activity, or a non-

communicative activity (Howarth, 2006). Reading is, of course, just as communicative as any language skills if teachers can perform a constructive role and carry out communicative activities in classrooms (Gao, 2008).

In order to make a communicative teaching situation to young learners, teachers should ensure the reading tasks comprehensive and is in fact comprehended. In fact, the tasks need not be complicated, especially in the early stages it is quite acceptable, and indeed very satisfying, for learners to carry simple actions and tasks. When setting a task, always give very clear instructions. For best results, the teacher must instruct most students directly, systematically, and explicitly. It is also important to allow the learners reasonable time to prepare and complete the assigned tasks or exercises.

New resources are constantly available in print or in electronic forms. As teachers, it is up to us to seek out updated materials that optimally benefit the learners and try to make use of new technology in teaching. As much as possible, teachers can bring in authentic materials that the learners can connect with, and that matches their needs and interests. Choosing, adapting, and supplementing teaching materials appropriately are important to involve the learners. Learners' interest in reading must be stimulated through regular exposure to interesting topics and through discussions in which the learners can respond to many kinds of texts. Young learners generally are keen on technology and new things; therefore, teachers hardly expect the young learners to be cooperative and motivated if the teachers do not change classroom routines.

To maintain learners' motivation and their engagement in class activities, it is desirable and necessary for teachers to create a comfortable and harmonious atmosphere where learners can enjoy communicating with others. Naturally, the learners may not be motivated if teachers do not involve them and let them take an active role in different class activities. "Giving students the chance to shine" is very important to encourage a cooperative classroom environment (Cabal, 2017).

Teachers' feedback is also important as it helps learning. Feedback may come in different forms as test results, appropriate error correction, or simply a smile on face. Teachers should take a positive attitude toward the learners' mistakes and take it in mind that errors are natural and inevitable in the process of learning and practicing. Avoid over-correcting. Don't undermine the learners' confidence by interrupting every single time they make a mistake. Learners of young age particularly need recognition from teachers (Gao, 2008). Praising can enhance the learners' achievement. Positive things are always encouraging. Start with the positive thing, and then tactfully move on to what needs to be improved.

A common situation in many IELTS reading classes is that young learners may have mixed levels of English. To accommodate the learners' variability, teachers should tailor lessons to individuals. Flipped learning can be beneficial when applied appropriately (Zainuddin & Halili, 2016). The aim of this instructional strategy is to give the learners time to assimilate the material at their own pace and provide a more active learning experience. Learners are introduced to some of the materials before class then practice, discuss, and activate the material during class time. In

a flipped classroom, teachers can give specific preparation tasks to different learners, provide specific support to individuals, and importantly can enable a more productive use of class time.

For young learners, it is necessary for teachers to organize communicative activities including movement. Learners are encouraged to change seats from time to time in pairwork or groupwork (Gao, 2008). Although these activities generally are limited in reading classes if compared with speaking classes but they are rewarding to engage the learners. Most exercises in IELTS reading can be done individually but teachers can assign the learners to check their work in pairs or small groups. Pair and group work helps learners to reflect on and explain how they have approached the task. This form of practice will help to develop a better understanding of exam strategies (Geyte, 2012).

Time management is very crucial in IELTS reading tests. Some learners emphasize on this difficulty because they fail to attend to all the questions within the time allotted. Young learners generally are fast, but without practice, time management in the examination is almost impossible. Learners are suggested to practice timed readings from mini-practice tests to complete ones. The IELTS reading has 40 questions from 3 sections which have to be answered in 60 minutes. The level of difficulty increases with each section, so learners need to allocate the time appropriately. Through experiment and practice, learners can develop a time management strategy for blocks of questions and individual question types.

Young learners generally love games and competitions, and teachers can keep their attention and engagement by making learning fun. Language games are highly motivating to learners because they “encourage learners to direct their energy towards learning by providing them with a meaningful context” (Adam (1993) as cited in Phuong & Nguyen, 2017). Exercises of vocabulary and scanning questions can be adapted into communicative games, giving the learners a nice opportunity to interact with each other, have fun and learn at the same time.

5 COMMUNICATIVE ACTIVITIES FOR TEACHING IELTS READING TO YOUNG LEARNERS

Communicative activities in classroom is an effective way to improve learners’ ability and their absorption of knowledge (Gao, 2008). Classroom activities guided by the communicative approach are characterized by trying to produce meaningful and real communication, at all levels. Gao (2008) suggested several categories of communicative activities, including topics arising from and relevant to the learners’ personal life, substantive topics which are educationally or professionally significant, and communicative classroom exercises.

For classroom activities for IELTS reading, Case (2011) proposed various activities from easy to challenging tasks (*see* Appendix). These activities can be modified and used as engaging activities through which learners can learn to use their ideas, pass on their ideas and receive ideas, and certainly to enlarge their vocabulary, broaden their knowledge and be more interested to read more and read better.

6 CONCLUSION

Teaching IELTS reading to young learners can be communicative, which helps to overcome some typical challenges faced by young learners in reading class. Implementing communicative activities in comfortable reading classroom will provide more opportunities for English language exposure and can engage learners more effectively.

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APPENDIX

Classroom Activities for IELTS Reading

A) Easytasks

- Give learners the right answers, and ask them to find the places in the text where the information is and underline the important sentences or words.
- Give the text with the important information underlined and ask learners to do the tasks by only looking at those bits.
- Give learners the text with the important information underlined and the questions mixed up. Learners match the questions to the underlined sections in the text and then answer them.
- Give learners the text(s) but no questions. Allow them to go home and read it as many times as they like with their dictionaries, but not write on the text. They then do the questions when they come into class.
- Give learners fewer options, or options in tasks where they usually only have a gap.
- Give learners the task with the answers filled in. Their task is to find the two or three questions that you have deliberately put the wrong answers in.

B) More fun tasks

- Give learners matching tasks (e.g. adding headings to paragraphs) with the texts cut up so they can shuffle them around on the table.
- Give learners one question at a time and ask them to shout out whenever they think they have found the right answer. Learners get one point for being first with the right answer and lose two points if they are wrong.
- Give learners one question and ask them to raise their hands when they think they have underlined the right part of the text and answered the question. When they all have their hands up, ask them the answer in the same order as they raised their hands. The first person to ask correctly gets the point.
- Put the text up the board, e.g. with a hugely blown up photocopy or by using an OHP, and ask two students to race to underline the part of the text that has the answer to the question you give them.
- Do IELTS-style tasks with more interesting texts that learners can discuss before and/ or after, e.g. a recent news story.

C) More useful tasks

- Ask learners to predict which things in the questions will be easiest to scan for and then time them as they look for and underline the answer to each one.

- Give learners texts that you have written on the topic of IELTS exam tactics to discuss before and after they do the exam tasks that you have written for them
- Give the texts with the questions cut off and all question numbers removed. Students match the questions to the texts before they try the tasks. This is good for skim reading.
- Give learners a text with all the answers wrong for different reasons, e.g. because they haven't followed the instructions, have used the one which is an example, or have looked at the wrong part of the text. They have to explain why those answers are wrong and then choose the right answer. This is good for spotting trick questions and avoiding common mistakes.

D) More challenging tasks

- Learners write questions for each other in one of the exam formats. You can give them some help with this, e.g. giving them a summary from which they can decide which words they will take out to make a text completion task.
- Learners do the question with less help than the actual task would give them, e.g. text completion without the mixed up missing words or adding paragraph headings just from their own ideas. You then give them the original questions.